

Barrier ID	Code	Definition	Number of participants	Quote example
C1	Newcomers experience social fears about working on challenging tasks	Participant explains newcomers' fearfulness of exposing a weakness or failing due to the socio-technical nature of OSS projects as a challenge for mentors.	4 (P1, P3, P4,P10)	P1: "Usually, because of social fear, they just back off. They think they aren't good enough or they don't know enough."
C2	Newcomers' lack of holistic understanding about the project	Participant describes newcomers' lack of comprehensive understanding about the project challenging for mentors due to the complex socio-technical landscape of projects and low newcomers' exposure to different parts of the code or tasks.	5 (P1, P2, P3,P4, P9)	P1: "when a newcomer comes in, one thing is they don't understand all the moving pieces of the codebase. Even if they get the code, they don't get the impact on the bigger scheme of things."
C3	Lack of information about how newcomer-friendly a task is	Participant describes lack of information about how newcomer-friendly a task is challenging to mentors, due to the existence of large number of tasks in issue trackers and lack of any direct way to spot tasks suitable for newcomers.	2 (P1,P10)	P1: "we don't know if things are suitable for newcomers." P10: "I dislike having things labeled as 'bite-size' because it may cause someone to skip talking to anyone and just grab something. You miss out on a lot of important social interaction."
C4	Difficulty in identifying the complexity of a task	Participant reports identifying the complexity of a task as a challenge for mentors. This represents how hard it is a task in terms of code complexity, domain knowledge, etc.	2 (P7, P8)	P8: "We don't have a good way [to evaluate the difficulty of a task]. (...) There's a lot out there to analyze the complexity of the code, but I've found none of it to be helpful in the Linux Kernel." P7: "A task may be more involved and technical than we thought initially. Then we may realize a task isn't suitable for someone because it's actually an expert level task."
C5	Difficulty in estimating the amount of time necessary to finish a task	Participant reports estimating the amount of time necessary to finish a task as a challenge to mentors. It is not always easy to predict the time to implement and deliver. This is important because newcomers are supposed to start with short-timed tasks	2 (P1, P8)	P8: "It's hard to estimate the time needed for a task. I'm not good at gauging what is appropriate for a newcomer."
C6	Lack of friendly tasks available for newcomers	Participant reports lack of easy-enough tasks available for newcomers at the time they join a project challenging for mentors. This is not related to lack of awareness (labels) or indications. This category represents the absence of tasks that would be suitable for a first-timer. This poses a challenge to the mentor who is trying to find a task.	3 (P2, P4, P5)	P2: "if you're a newcomer and come at a time when there aren't many tasks open for newcomers, . . . then the difficulty lies in finding something in a certain application to turn into a newcomer task"
C7	Lack of available information about newcomer's skills, interest, and expertise	Participant describes lack of available information about newcomer's skills, interest, and expertise challenging for mentors. Knowing newcomer's interests and expertise may make a difference, because finding a matching task would make it more exciting and easy for the newcomer. The mentors reported that it is a problem to correctly identify newcomer's expertise and skills.	4 (P2, P4, P7, P9)	P9: "sometimes you think they can take on more than they, in reality, are capable of." P4: "some [newcomers] are very good but they don't have some work portfolio to show their previous skills."

Strategy category	Strategy name	Definition	Number of participants	Quote example
Identify task complexity	Reproducing the bug	Participant describes reproducing the bug as a strategy to identify task complexity as it helps in further understanding the bug and fixing it.	1(P2)	P2: "First of all, we reproduce the bug and try to see what is causing it and find out what is necessary to fix it. Then we assess whether the skill level is similar to what a newcomer would have to fix it."
	Comparing the complexity of new bugs with existing bugs in bug tracker	Participant describes comparing the complexity of new bugs with existing bugs in bug tracker as a strategy to identify task complexity as the previously tagged issues can serve as a scale.	1(P2)	P2: "we use, for example, the bug tracker to figure out if a bug is at the same level as other newcomer bugs we have."
	Tagging the task based on difficulty	Participant describes tagging the task based on difficulty as a strategy to identify task complexity as it helps in making newcomer-friendly tasks more visible to and identifiable by mentors and newcomers.	6 (P1,P2, P4,P5,P6,P7)	P4: "we have this tool called Bugzilla, which we are tracking all the bugs. When we file a bug we find to be easy; instead of going directly to fix it, we tag it with a newcomer tag so that we have in our website a list of bugs that are suitable for newcomers."
	Adding documentation	Participant describes adding documentation as a strategy to identify task complexity as it helps in further understanding the task.	2 (P2,P4)	P4: "we put in the description how we want the contribution to be and which file they should look at. So we are pretty much tagging bugs and creating tutorials on how to fix this specific bug so they can learn the whole process of how to make their contribution." "You look at the description of the task, you should be able to see if it requires familiarity with C, JavaScript, regular expressions, etc."
	Discussing tagging in the conferences	Participant describes discussing tagging in conferences as a strategy to help improve tagging of tasks.	1 (P1)	P1: "Some committers get together at conferences and meetups to discuss ideas to help newcomers when getting involved... We discuss tagging at those conferences."
Identify skills required for finishing a task	Breaking the code into sections and identify the concepts/algorithms	Participant describes breaking the code into sections as a strategy to identify skills required for finishing a task as it helps in identify the involved concepts/algorithms.	3 (P5, P6, P10)	P5: "To measure the skills, I go through the code line by line and break it into sections to tell what concepts are needed. I determine what algorithms they would need to know, what hardware they need to know, and what coding skills they need to work the bug."
	Forming a mental model to help assess a task	Participant describes mentors forming a mental model to help assess a task as a strategy to identify skills required for finishing a task.	2 (P6, P10)	P6: "When I see a task, I can make a mental model of where it may fit."
Identify newcomer's characteristics	Asking newcomers directly about their interests and expertise	Participants reports asking newcomers directly about their interests and expertise, as a strategy to identify newcomers' characteristics.	7(P1,P3,P4,P6,P7,P9,P10)	P10: "I try to talk to them and help them before sending them off to look at the issue tracker. I gauge their interests and their mindset about the process to find a task for them."
	Evaluating previous contributions	Participants reports evaluating previous contributions, as a strategy to identify newcomers' characteristics as it provides evidence about newcomers' expertise.	3 (P4, P9, P10)	P4: "If we have some way to see past contributions of the newcomer, you can easily see it is something related to that they have done before."
	Assigning a small task first and then challenging the newcomers with bigger tasks	Participant reports assigning a small task first and then challenging the newcomers with bigger tasks as a method to evaluate newcomers' skills and interests and support them through the learning curve.	2 (P3, P7)	P7: "Sometimes you have to start on the basic tasks and go from there. We see how they are doing and then move forward."

Scaffold newcomer's skill acquisition	Recommending repetitive tasks	Participant reports recommending repetitive tasks to help the newcomers master specific skills and gain confidence before they move to more complex tasks.	1 (P3)	P3: "I usually choose tasks that are repetitive but not very technical, so maybe modifying many lines of code in the same way. It is not very technical, but then they learn a bit more about the programming language or the API."
Restructure project's task landscape	Dividing tasks into smaller pieces	Participant reports dividing tasks into smaller pieces as a strategy to better restructure the project landscape.	2 (P2, P3)	P3: "usually we can divide the tasks based on the project itself and knowledge about specific parts of the project."
	Encouraging newcomers to add functionalities	Participant reports encouraging newcomers to add functionalities as a strategy to better restructure the project landscape.	1 (P5)	P5: "In Gnome To Do, in the beginning, there were 6 tasks which were big and not suited to newcomers. Because I didn't have any easily fixable tasks, I encouraged newcomers to add new functionality as a way to contribute."